

A Geospatial Activity Modification Framework for Calibrating Mobility Models

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Introduction

Urban mobility and transport can be viewed as a complex system consisting of multiple components, including physical infrastructures (e.g., road networks) and behavioural actors (e.g., car drivers). Changes in one component can have a propagating effect on the rest of the system. This is particularly relevant in transport systems due to the behavioural heterogeneity of their actors, including daily activity scheduling of travellers. Understanding these complex dynamics is critical for identifying the impact of transport policies or system shocks. In these cases, simulation models of complex systems, for example mobility microsimulation models and Agent-Based Models (ABMs) are particularly useful.

Mobility microsimulation models represent individuals and/or vehicles as entities with agency (agents) who interact with a geospatial network (space) – and with each other in the case of ABMs (Crooks, Heppenstall, and Malleson 2017; Heppenstall et al. 2012). A subset category of such models is data-driven models which can be calibrated to different geospatial contexts, heterogeneous populations and daily activity schedules. These models are calibrated following two different approaches. First, synthetic activity schedules are generated that can be calibrated alongside other trip parameters (e.g., POLARIS (Polaris team 2025)). However, this can lead to mismatches between the distributions of the generated and empirical activities (Auld et al. 2011). Furthermore, the synthetic activity sequences are not often validated using empirical sequences in travel diaries (e.g., ADAPTS (Auld et al. 2011)). The second approach involves the use of other models to generate fixed activity schedules by matching empirical data to synthetic populations. This allows agents to calibrate other parameters of their trips, such as route choices (e.g., MATSim (Axhausen, Horni, and Nagel 2016) and TRANSIMS (Nagel et al. 1997)). This approach assumes that the allocated activities are valid, which ignores the uncertainties embedded in the geospatial allocation of the synthetic population.

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To address this, we propose a framework for activity modifications during mobility models calibration without disrupting the empirical activity sequences or distributions. This can minimise the uncertainties in the geospatial allocation of the activity schedules to synthetic populations in mobility models. We showcase a constrained application of the framework using an abstract mobility ABM in the context Tillydrone, Aberdeen, UK.

The next section outlines the activity modification framework. Section 3 outlines an initial application to showcase the proposed framework using a constrained ABM. It also highlights preliminary results. Section 4 reflects on the relevance of the framework and outlines future work.

Methodology: Activity modification framework

The activity modification framework introduces an approach for spatially switching activity schedules between simulated individuals without changing the activities sequences. The framework is designed assuming an available synthetic population in a mobility ABM with assigned activity schedules and target destinations. The framework consists of six key steps as shown in figure 2.

First, the mobility model optimises the trips for each individual without modifying activities. Subsequently, the model reports trip times per activity.

Second, the mismatches between the empirical and trip times are identified by calculating the raw errors and MSD. Signed errors are calculated for each individual trip as shown in equation 1, whereas the MSD is calculated for all the trips of a household as shown in equation 2.

$$e_p = t_p^{sim} - t_p^{obs} \quad (1)$$

$$MSD_h = \frac{\sum_{p \in P_h} (t_p^{sim} - t_p^{obs})}{n_h} \quad (2)$$

where e_p is the signed error for a trip p , t_p^{sim} is the simulated time, t_p^{obs} is the observed time, MSD_h is the mean signed error for a household h , P_h is the set of trips made within the household h and n_h is the number of trips made by the household. It is important to note that a positive e_p implies that the simulated time is longer than the observed one and vice versa, and a positive MSD_h implies that overall the household has longer simulated and vice versa.

Third, once the MSDs and errors are calculated for all households and individuals, a set of households (H) with an absolute MSD exceeding a defined threshold are identified ($|MSD_h| > \mu$). The maximum number of selected households is capped to a value m – this controls the number of activity modifications applied hereafter.

Fourth, for each household in H , the trip associated with the highest absolute error ($p_{max(|e_p|)}$) in that household is selected. The numeric sign of the error (e_p) indicates whether the origin of the trip needs to be closer to ($e_p > 0$) or farther from ($e_p < 0$) its destination. Accordingly, a radial geospatial zone around the destination is identified between the radial distance to the origin of the trip r_o and a defined radius r as shown in figure 1.

Fifth, within each zone associated with a considered household (h^{con}), a set of households with a

Figure 1: Radial geospatial zones at (a) $e_p < 0$ and (b) $e_p > 0$

similar number of individuals as h^{con} and non-identical schedules with h^{con} are identified. Within the defined set, the household (h^{sim}) with the lowest attribute space difference compared to h^{con} is selected. The individuals in h^{con} and h^{sim} are matched to achieve the lowest attribute space difference between each pair as shown in equations 3-5.

$$y_{i,j} = \sum_{k \in K} s_{ij|k} + \sum_{k \in K'} g_{ij|k} \quad (3)$$

$$s_{i,j|k} = \frac{|a_{k,i} - a_{k,j}|}{\max(|a_{k,i} - a_{k,j}|)} \quad (4)$$

$$g_{i,j|k} = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } a_{k,i} = a_{k,j} \\ 1, & \text{if } a_{k,i} \neq a_{k,j} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where $y_{i,j}$ is the total attribute space difference between two individual/households i and individual/households j , K is the set of continuous attributes, K' is the set of categorical attributes, $s_{i,j|k}$ and $g_{i,j|k}$ are the attribute space difference assuming k is a continuous and categorical variable respectively.

Finally, activities are then switched between each matched pair, which implies a switch of the origin of the trip in h^{con} yielding a high error. Overall, this ensures that activity switching is applied between structurally similar households and demographically similar individuals.

The simulated ABM trip times and activity modifications are repeated until all households are below the MSD threshold ($|MSD_h| < \mu$). This can take multiple iterations based on the number of modification cap m .

Preliminary application and results

To showcase the framework, we apply it in the context of Tillydrone, Aberdeen (Scotland). We use a dummy synthetic population of 1000 individuals with age and gender distribution matching the UK census (Office for National Statistics 2025). The synthetic population is matched to the National Travel Survey (NTS) data (Department for Transport 2023) using the age and gender parameters only.

To allocate destinations and simulate trip times, we use a constrained version of the mobility ABM MATraM (Gamal et al. 2026). The ABM includes vehicle agents that move between building

Figure 2: Activity modification schematic framework

to achieve a set of daily activities (as shown in figure 3). Vehicles find the quickest route to their destination based on congestion patterns. Each 100 time steps represent 1 second. At initialisation, the dummy synthetic population is randomly assigned to buildings representing homes. During the runs, vehicles move to their destinations, monitor their trip times and return home at the end of the day. For a detailed description of MATraM, see Gamal et al. (2026).

Figure 3: Mobility ABM agents and space representation for the case of Tillydrone, Aberdeen

In the activity modifications phase, we do not restrict the selection of similar individuals to geospatial zones. We set $\mu = 0$ to effectively include any minor MSD_h . We repeat one iteration from the initial state with the number of activity modifications capped at $m = 250$, $m = 500$ and $m = 1000$ individuals. To identify the degree the simulated trip times match in the system, we report the Mean Squared Error (MSE) of all households as shown in equation 6 – as MSD can underestimate errors in the whole system.

$$MSE = \frac{\sum_{p \in P} (t_p^{sim} - t_p^{obs})^2}{N} \quad (6)$$

Where MSE is the mean squared error and P is the set of trips made in the whole system.

The results show a decrease in the MSE from 0.15 to 0.144 (at $m = 250$), 0.143 (at $m = 500$) and 0.14 (at $m = 1000$) (see figure 4). This indicates that a higher number of modifications in one iteration improves the match between empirical and simulated times. These results are promising as higher performance is achieved despite the random geospatial selection of individuals. Considering geospatial zones is expected to further improve the achieved matches.

Figure 4: MSE results per activities modifications cap m

Conclusion

Mobility models are initialised with the uncertainties in the geospatial allocation of households and their activity schedules. To address this, we proposed an activity modification framework calibrating mobility models without disrupting the empirical trips distributions or sequences. A constrained application in Tillydrone, Aberdeen showcased the capacity of the framework to improve the match between empirical trip times and simulated ones. This is promising as it allows for generating a synthetic population with activities that more closely resemble reality. We plan on further extending the study to include: (1) an application testing considering geospatial zones during activity modifications; and (2) a sensitivity analysis for the MSD threshold (μ) and the modifications (m).

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